
CSCCE Tech Case Study: Using GitHub teams to manage contributor access to Rosetta

About this case study

In 2023, CSCCE hosted a series of community “Tools Trials” that focused on tools commonly used for community management in open-source and open-source-supporting communities. The goal of the series - which consisted of several live webinars with Q&A and this accompanying tip sheet collection - was to share existing knowledge and provide any scientific community manager with options about tools and use cases they could explore further.

One of the most commonly used tools by these communities is GitHub. In this case study, we summarize how the Rosetta project uses GitHub teams to manage contributions to their open-source code base.

What is GitHub?

[GitHub](#) is a version control platform for storing, collaborating on, and tracking projects. It is primarily used for software development, but can also be used for other collaborative work. It utilizes [Git](#), which is an open-source version control system that can track which users make changes to computer files (e.g., code, documents) and when. Although there are other software platforms that use Git, GitHub is the most popular. [Check out our introductory tip sheet for more information.](#)

Overview of Rosetta

Rosetta is a molecular modeling software product that is licensed to commercial and non-commercial users, and has recently (spring 2024) transitioned to an open repository. [RosettaCommons](#) is the community of Rosetta developers and users that work together on the software using GitHub. To join RosettaCommons, a researcher needs to become a lab member or a collaborator of any of the ~100 RosettaCommons labs around the world. Community members contribute to the maintenance and development of the code base, but not all members choose to do so.

Using GitHub teams to manage contributor access

[GitHub teams](#) is a function of a GitHub organization that allows you, as an organization owner, to assign [permissions](#) to different groups of users. Permissions on GitHub teams are inclusive or stacked. This means that the lowest level has READ permissions, the second level has READ and WRITE permissions, and the most permissive level has ADMIN permissions, which include READ and WRITE.

You can also use the teams function to send notifications to all of the members of the team, request people from a team to review items, and nest teams (child teams inherit the permissions of their parent team). @mentioning a team by name automatically notifies all of the members of the team, and each team has a page in GitHub, on which all the members are listed as well as the repositories to which they contribute.

SETTING UP A TEAM IN GITHUB

1. Go to the teams tab within your organization:

2. Click the green button on the right:

3. From here you can create a new team, enter a brief description, select the parent team (if applicable), and select visibility and team notifications.
4. After you created the team, you can add members and repositories to the team. Note that each repository that you add can have different permissions (READ, WRITE, or ADMIN).
5. You can add members to the team either under the team tab (green button) or when you invite them directly to the organization on GitHub.

Pros and cons of using GitHub for this use case

[For general pros and cons of using GitHub for community management, [please refer to our overview tip sheet.](#)]

Pros:

- GitHub teams allows you to give different permissions to different repositories in your organization. For example, you might want to invite some users to view but not change some of the more sensitive code repositories. Controlling the permissions you give to various users can empower champions to do more in your community.
- The teams function allows you to easily communicate with sub-groups of your community through notifications.

Cons:

- You need to be logged in to GitHub to join a team and, therefore, have some level of comfort using the platform. Someone without a profile or unfamiliar with the platform may not feel included to participate.
- Over time, permissions to access a repository may need to change among members of the community. Maintenance of these permissions may be time intensive if managing teams for numerous repositories. Having clear onboarding and offboarding pathways for team members will be important.

Additional resources

- [Julia Koehler Leman's full presentation on using GitHub teams](#) - Watch this case study being presented during CSCCE's Tools Trial in this short video
- About GitHub teams: <https://docs.github.com/en/organizations/organizing-members-into-teams/about-teams>

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Citing and reusing this tip sheet

CITATION AND REUSE

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